

SecureExecutor: An Automated Way to Leverage SCONE to Enhance Application Security

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Abstract—Providing security guarantees when executing application code in untrusted environments is vital, especially when handling sensitive data. To address this task, Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) such as Intel’s Software Guard eXtension (SGX), which implement hardware-based techniques by silicon manufacturers, have been introduced to provide confidentiality and integrity in remote execution. Library OS technologies, e.g., SCONE, aim to facilitate the adoption of TEEs in software development. Despite their essential help, these technologies still require significant effort from developers. In this paper, we introduce SECUREEXECUTOR, a Linux utility that aims to simplify and automate leveraging SCONE in SGX enclaves, i.e., isolated memory areas. We analyze the design and the internal schema that SECUREEXECUTOR follows, outlining the steps of its usage. We further apply it to three real-world open-source projects, validating its application and providing important insights.

Index Terms—Security, TEE, Intel SGX, SCONE

I. INTRODUCTION

The new technological advancements in cloud computing infrastructures and the need to move the data closer to where they are computed and consumed have created the need to run application code on machines outside the developers’ control. To provide a level of trust, hardware-based Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) technologies [1]–[3] have emerged to provide confidentiality and integrity guarantees against strong adversaries, such as a cloud provider, that have privileged access to the machines on which the code is running, and the data are generated. These security properties are guaranteed by establishing a root of trust in the system design, which serves as a Trusted Computing Base (TCB). This occasionally entails hardware, software, or any other critical component used to ensure reliability. The hardware, being the less replaceable and unmodifiable part of a system, has led silicon manufacturers to integrate hardware-based techniques into their chips to address the trusted remote computation problem.

In Software Guard eXtension (SGX), Intel’s TEE technology, the CPU provides secure enclaves, i.e., dedicated isolated memory areas, which can be used to shield the code and the generated data against attackers with root or physical access rights. However, the amount of protected memory in the enclave is small, and also the system call interface from inside the enclave is limited. These limitations make the adoption of SGX by application developers, not a trivial task.

Library OS architectures [4]–[7] such as SCONE have emerged to ease the adoption of SGX architecture. These technologies allow applications to run into an SGX enclave transparently, requiring minimal code modification by developers. LibOS architectures significantly help software development, yet they still demand a considerable amount of effort to specify the proper parameters, download dependencies, and go through several intermediate steps.

In this paper, we present SECUREEXECUTOR, an automation tool that aims to fully automate the process of adopting the SGX features by applications. SECUREEXECUTOR builds on SCONE, relieving the developer of the burden of walking through the intermediate steps that the SCONE necessitates.

Overall, this paper makes the following key contributions:

- **SECUREEXECUTOR**: We designed a tool we call SECUREEXECUTOR. This tool empowers developers by automating the process of running applications inside SGX enclaves, thus contributing to enhanced application security.
- *Resources-Available Implementation*: SECUREEXECUTOR builds upon the SCONE architecture and is implemented in Bash. The implementation provides a plug-and-play solution to software developers who want to enable the execution of their applications on enclaves deployed across physical machines.
- *Empirical Evaluation*: We evaluate SECUREEXECUTOR across three applications targeting three programming environments: Rust, Python, and C++. The use cases show SECUREEXECUTOR’s competence in facilitating the development process when these programming languages are used.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. Intel SGX

Hardware-based Trusted Execution Environments (TEE) like ARM TrustZone, Intel Software Guard Extension (SGX), and AMD Secure Execution Virtualization (SEV) are frequently used to provide code/data integrity and confidentiality. This work concentrates on x86-based devices, specifically Intel SGX, applicable to both high-performance computation infrastructures (Xeon CPUs) and low-computation edge devices (Intel NUC), operating under similar principles.

Intel introduced its implementation of TEE with the development of Intel SGX back in 2015. Unlike the previously security-related methods utilized, like Trusted Platform Module (TPM) and Trusted Execution Technology (TXT), this approach employs a smaller TCB that relies exclusively on code and data, without the necessity to measure the entire software stack or system in which the code is running.

The primary concept behind SGX is the establishment of trusted containers known as enclaves. Enclaves are encrypted memory regions within Dynamic Random-Access Memory (DRAM), inaccessible to higher privilege software such as Hypervisor or Operating Systems (OSs). Software developers can leverage SGX-enabled processors to create enclaves by following Intel’s SGX programming model. They can allocate Enclave Page Cache (EPC) pages inside the Processor Reserved Memory (PRM) to store enclave code and data. Due to the fact that PRM is a specialized section of DRAM that sticks to strict security policies, the isolation of enclaves from other software, e.g. kernel or System Management Mode (SMM) code, is possible. In addition to its other purposes, Enclave Page Cache Map (EPCM) can also enable the isolation between enclaves. These capabilities, implemented by the hardware, make possible the protection of sensitive data, and keep the confidentiality of security-sensitive computations [1].

Another novel aspect of SGX, and a significant deviation from TPM and TXT, is that SGX is closely associated with software attestation principles. After enclave initialization, a cryptographic hash of it can be generated, according to hardware-based cryptographic instructions. This hash serves as the identity of the enclave, which can ensure a certain level of trust. Each modification of the enclave will result in a different hash, hence, we can rely only on specific enclaves. A mandatory step to confirm the integrity of the code executed in an enclave that exist in a remote party [1].

B. LibOS

Running an application inside SGX enclaves is a time-consuming process that demands a deep understanding of the underlying framework [1]. To facilitate this process, Library Operating System (LibOS) technologies have been proposed that provide a ‘lift and shift’ principle, allowing application developers to leverage the SGX framework with limited modifications.

SCONE and Gramine are two of the most well-known LibOS options that allow existing software to support SGX without rewriting the whole code [8]. SCONE [4] provides a *secure container* integrated with the Docker container environment to ease application deployment. It offers a shielded interface that validates the system calls, guarantees confidentiality and integrity for the application files and encrypts the network traffic, which supports an M:N threading model by mapping N operating system threads to M applications threads inside the enclave. To use SCONE, the application has to be statically linked against the SCONE libraries; thus, recompilation of the source code has to be executed.

Gramine [5] is another LibOS framework that aims to reduce the developer’s effort to execute their application inside an enclave that adopts an 1:1 threading modelling. Opposite to SCONE, Gramine supports dynamic linking by incorporating the Gramine library OS [9] in the enclave. The enclave and the host operating system communicate through a Platform Adaptation Layer (PAL), which is considered as untrusted. To secure the application Gramine implements shielding by verifying the hash of application-loaded libraries, implementing a custom Application Binary Interface (ABI) and using the TLS protocol for the communication between enclaves.

Other LibOS include Haven [6] EleOS [7], SGX-LKL [10] and Panoply [11]. SGX-LKL allows the execution of syscalls directly inside the SGX enclave by leveraging the Linux Kernel Library. EleOS, apart from syscalls, also performs inside the enclave a user-managed virtual memory. Haven underpins explicitly the execution of Windows applications inside enclaves whereas Panoply’s primary goal is to reduce the demand of the TCB.

C. Automation Tools

The different LibOS technologies, even if they facilitate the leverage of SGX enclaves by developers still, they demand a significant amount of effort. SGXPy [12] improves the compatibility of Python applications with LibOS by finding automatically and accurately all the dependent files and imposing file access permissions, SGX-PySpark [13] shows how we can integrate PySpark framework for data analytics with SCONE, whereas TensorSCONE [14] integrates into SCONE the TensorFlow, a machine learning framework.

Specifically for SCONE, a significant burden is imposed by the static linking that demands manually tuning of different required parameters. SGXTuner [15] reduced the configuration time but also improved the performance of SGX-enabled applications by allowing an optimal stochastic parameter selection for different LibOS and specifically the ETHREADS, STHREADS, ESPINS, SSPINS, ESLEEP and SSLEEP parameters for SCONE.

Similar to SGXTuner, SECUREEXECUTOR aims to provide an automated process of the configuration phase for the SCONE LibOS. However, it focuses on different binary parameters, *i.e.*, the ones that are demanding in order to allow applications to run on enclaves deployed across real devices, automating the entire process.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

SCONE facilitates the integration of application source code into SGX enclaves. Its main goal is to enable application execution with minimal or no source code modification. SCONE provides significant help to developers who want to enhance the security of their applications; however, it does not offer a fully automated integration. Developers still need to make their applications fully compatible with the SCONE TEE framework by downloading dependencies, specifying required parameters, and rebuilding their applications against the TEE conversion tooling provided by SCONE.

Fig. 1. C++ project structure

Making an application SGX-enabled should follow a plug-and-play approach, *i.e.*, removing the developer from the whole process by having a tool that initiates and completes all the necessary steps. Automating the sconification process would contribute to releasing better and more secure applications in the market. Such a tool should provide the below key functionalities:

- A *Interoperability*: Different applications demand different dependencies based on the use case, resulting in a different number of intermediate steps in the sconification process. The designed tool should aim to support all application projects, from basic to more advanced.
- B *Extensibility*: The sconification process depends on the programming language used by the application each time. A tool must be able to support many different languages, starting with the most common ones and aiming to support progressively more.
- C *Automation*: The tool should select the required parameters based on the developer’s ultimate goal, *i.e.*, running the application on simulated enclaves or real devices supporting the SGX framework, without demanding any further effort by the developer other than a specified flag.

SECUREEXECUTOR builds on this vision, aiming to provide an automation process to developers who want to secure their applications by adopting the SGX framework. In particular, it targets projects that implement minimal programming models of computation, *i.e.*, lambda function, developed in Rust, C++ or Python, assisting developers in realising the execution of their application in real devices that support the Intel SGX enclaves. In the following sections, we elaborate more on the SECUREEXECUTOR internals and exemplify its application in three use cases.

IV. SECUREEXECUTOR

SECUREEXECUTOR is a Linux utility implemented in Bash, designed to simplify the process of leveraging SCONE for developers. It provides a layer of abstraction, removing the need for developers to remember all the complex steps and parameters required to create and run trusted containers. With its comprehensive set of flags and arguments, SECUREEXECUTOR automates the process of building and running applications in trusted Docker containers. These applications can implement minimal programming models of computation, such as lambda functions, and can be written in C++, Python, or Rust.

```

json lambda_handler(json& event, json&
context) {
    // TODO: implement your lambda function

    // Create response
    json response = { {"status", "success"}
};
    return response;
}

```

Listing 1. Lambda Function in C++

For each programming language, SECUREEXECUTOR offers a flexible template project structure and an API that mirrors the AWS lambda functions API. These two resources serve as guides for developers, empowering them to implement their desired code inside secure enclaves. However, it’s important to note that they should be viewed as references and extended to meet the unique requirements of each application.

SECUREEXECUTOR’s flags allow a consistent procedure to be followed across the three supported programming languages when generating a new project. To start, the user runs an initialization command, specifying the programming language of the application as a flag. For instance, to generate a new lambda in C++, the user would run the command: `./SecureExecutor -cpp -lambda-name helloworld -new`. The tool then creates a new project containing the necessary files to create the secure containers. Figure 1 illustrates the project structure for a C++ application created after executing the command above.

The `lambda_function.cpp` file incorporates the Listing 1 inside which the developers can place the lambda function code. Inside the `CMakeList.txt`, the developers can specify the libraries and frameworks that are required by their application and need to be installed indirectly. A `Cargo.toml` and a `Requirements.txt` file serve the same purpose in case the lambda function is written in Python and Rust, respectively. After placing the application code and specifying the application dependencies, the developer — assuming that the execution environment supports the required dependencies — can further use SECUREEXECUTOR to build the trusted Docker images. SECUREEXECUTOR has automate this step in a single command, *e.g.*, `./SecureExecutor -cpp -lambda-name helloworld -build` for our C++ example. The secure image of the application is created after running the building command and is ready to run on an SGX-enabled device.

Regardless of the implementation language *i.e.*, C++, Python, and Rust, SECUREEXECUTOR offers a similar internal process to build the trusted images. The basic building block of SECUREEXECUTOR is the *sconecuratedimages*. Into these base images, SECUREEXECUTOR installs additional generic software like OpenSSL. Then, when the user requests to build a secure image of an application, SECUREEXECUTOR places the target project tree inside the images and incorporates any extra dependencies. For C++ and Rust, the final step involves compiling the code. The generated image by SECUREEXECUTOR contains everything needed for execution; thus, the user

can run the container by executing a single command, e.g., `./SecureExecutor -cpp -lambda-name helloworld -run` in the case of a C++ implementation.

In the next section, we shift our focus from individual lambda functions to entire projects. We examine how to extend SECUREEXECUTOR to automate the process comprehensively.

V. USE CASES

SECUREEXECUTOR, fully automates the process for lambda functions. The final goal is to achieve the same behavior in already-developed projects. This section describes the experiments conducted on open-source repositories on GitHub. We selected one application for each supported programming language — C++, Python, and Rust. Examples demonstrate that each project may require a different building process to generate the trusted image. Our experiments still have some hard-coded configurations to build the described examples. For now, users can automatically create and run only these specific predefined applications in different environments. Even though this could be considered a drawback, it is an essential intermediate step that aims to find clever ways to automate the process for a broader range of projects. Our future goal is to extend the abilities of SECUREEXECUTOR to solve the initial problem.

The experiments below confirm that SECUREEXECUTOR simplifies enhancing applications’ defense capabilities by utilizing SCONE. SCONE can then protect apps from threats, ensure authorized access, and prevent data breaches. A simplified approach without the overhead of in-depth knowledge of fundamental SGX principles. Due to the automation SECUREEXECUTOR provides, the likelihood of human errors during the integration of enclaves is reduced.

A. Experimental Setup

All experiments should be conducted in real-world enclaves. Therefore, the selection of SGX-ready hardware was mandatory. Since one of the current trends is to offload computations to edge nodes with limited capabilities (see V-B1), the hardware selected is a small form factor computer with similar capacities. For completeness, below we present the hardware and software characteristics of the system utilized during the execution of the cases:

- Host: NUC10i7FNK
- OS: Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS x86_64
- Kernel: 5.19.0
- SGX Driver: Out-of-tree Driver (/dev/isgx)
- SGX Version: SGX1

B. Use Cases

In our case, when referring to the hard-coded configuration, we mean the additional application-specific Dockerfiles created. SECUREEXECUTOR generates base Docker images (see section IV). For these specific use cases, the newly created Dockerfiles extend the base ones and internally follow the documentation of each repository to build the confidential

executables. SECUREEXECUTOR is also utilized to build and run the applications. Moreover, the application-specific Dockerfiles can be written without considering SGX. Thus, only the environment is configured based on the building process that each software requires.

1) *Use Case 1: EDGELESS Distributed System:* EDGELESS [16] is a European-developed project that builds a framework that enables serverless edge computing. It is mainly intended for edge nodes with limited capabilities, and one of its goals is to secure these nodes by leveraging the specialized hardware they support, such as Intel SGX.

Fig. 2. EDGELESS system Overview

In the EDGELESS architecture, a cluster consists of one or more orchestration domains (three in the example in Figure 2) managed by an ϵ -CON (controller).

Users interact with the ϵ -CON to request the creation of workflows. A workflow specifies how several functions and resources should interact to compose the service requested by the user by sending asynchronous events akin to function invocations to one another. Functions live entirely within the realm of the EDGELESS runtime, while resources may interact with the external environment, e.g., handling events in a resource may have a side effect, such as updating an entry on an external in-memory database or reading the value of a physical sensor.

Functions are stateful: a given function instance is assigned to exactly one workflow. Thus, the function developer may assume that data will generally remain available across multiple invocations on the same function instance. However, such a state is:

- tied to the specific instance: if there are multiple instances for the same function, then there is no consistency guarantee across the multiple states;
- ephemeral: if a function instance is terminated, then there is no effort to save/persist the state.

As described, one of the main objectives of this project is to secure the functions executed inside the EDGELESS_NODE. SECUREEXECUTOR aims to automate the process and solve this problem. It will generate the secure image of the trusted

node and execute functions inside enclaves providing security guarantees such as confidentiality.

Due to the project’s complexity, the internal process for generating the `EDGELESS_NODE` image follows a 3-stage process. This process is a bit different from the single file configuration introduced at the beginning of the section, which we are trying to follow in the subsequent two use cases. Nevertheless, this characteristic of the study should be considered for the following versions of the tool.

First, we create a native Rust Docker environment where all `EDGELESS_NODE` prerequisites are installed. Then, `SECUREEXECUTOR` clones `EDGELESS_NODE` sources from the `EDGELESS` official GitHub page [16], followed by `EDGELESS_NODE` code compilation. At the end of this stage, we obtain the untrusted executable of the `EDGELESS_NODE`. We would utilize this executable if we did not run `EDGELESS_NODE` inside a TEE. In the second stage, a `SCONE` container is deployed to run the *scone-signer* and convert the untrusted image to a trusted one. Finally, we leverage one of the *sconecuratedimages* as a runtime environment to execute the confidential binary.

Although multiple steps are required to build the trusted image of the `EDGELESS_NODE`, a single `SECUREEXECUTOR` command: `./SecureExecutor -edgeless-node -build` automates this process. When this command is requested, a directory appears (`edgeless_node`). The trusted binary of `EDGELESS_NODE` and the *node.toml* configuration files are generated in this directory. *node.toml* needs to be modified based on the `EDGELESS` instructions to connect with the `EDGELESS` system. With a working *node.toml*, the execution of `./SecureExecutor -edgeless-node -run` is the final step to verify that the trusted node can establish a connection with the `EDGELESS` system and verify `SECUREEXECUTOR` behavior (Figure 3).

2) *Use Case 2: Python Application:* To make sure that `SECUREEXECUTOR` can successfully build and run a generic Python project, we conducted some experiments with *Depix* [17] project located on GitHub. The code in this repository is used to recover plaintext from pixelized screenshots and has more than 25K stars. Since it is not as complex as Use Case **V-B1**, we followed the single file configuration approach introduced at the beginning of the section.

Regarding *Depix*, the only step we had to do was to develop the application-specific Dockerfile. `SECUREEXECUTOR` could then build and run its trusted image without code modifications. The only requirements were: a) the generated Dockerfile to be based on `SECUREEXECUTOR` base Python image and b) to install the external dependencies (which were not specified in a *requirements.txt* file).

3) *Use Case 3: C++ Application:* The last implementation demonstrates the proposed `SECUREEXECUTOR` behavior in a C++-based application. We created a trusted image for a security-oriented application [18]. This project leverages custom implementations of SHA256, AES, and CRC32 to secure and embed a file in a picture using steganography

principles. This case also utilizes the single file configuration approach.

Similarly to the Python implementation, the process was straightforward. We only had to develop the appropriate Dockerfile following the repository documentation to build and run the executable.

VI. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

A. Limitations

`SECUREEXECUTOR`, despite its promising capabilities, currently has some known limitations that should be addressed in this research and fixed in its future versions. One of them is that the Python implementation does not support widespread machine learning frameworks like PyTorch and TensorFlow for CPU computations. For Rust, WebAssembly has yet to be supported. However, integration of WebAssembly is in progress for future updates.

Only Lambda functions are fully automated, but extending this automation to more applications is still a work in progress, dependent on ongoing research and development. External libraries and dependencies are managed indirectly within standard files, i.e. `CMakeLists.txt`, `Cargo.toml`, and `requirements.txt`, but in some cases, a manual direct installation in the system could be required.

B. Future Work

The current study has space for improvements based on the findings extracted. Hence, several areas of future work can be discussed. Firstly, more limitations like the ones mentioned above should be addressed, and developing feasible workarounds is essential for the tool’s robustness. Then, expanding `SECUREEXECUTOR` to support additional languages will help understand language-specific challenges and opportunities.

Experimenting with a wide range of complex projects that incorporate numerous external dependencies is fundamental to ensuring the scalability of our approach to real-world projects. Crucial is to investigate projects that utilize multiple languages simultaneously and highlight interoperability issues & integration challenges, which will assist in developing a powerful tool. Attestation principles should also be automatically integrated into the tool, and the proper mechanisms should be incorporated to automate related processes.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we present `SECUREEXECUTOR`, a Linux utility implemented in Bash that is designed to alleviate the complexities of TEE integration by fully automating the application of `SCONE LibOS` in software development. It minimizes developers’ effort in converting applications into secure Docker containers that can be deployed across real devices. Our experiments show our tool’s effectiveness across different scenarios. Future updates will expand language support and improve automation, making `SECUREEXECUTOR` a practical tool for securing various applications.

<pre> -u-ORC /home/user/edgeless/target/debug # RUST_LOG=Info ./edgeless_con_d [2024-05-16T14:23:34Z INFO edgeless_con] Starting Edgeless Controller at http://192.168.11.2:7001 [2024-05-16T14:23:34Z INFO edgeless_con] Starting Edgeless Controller at http://192.168.11.2:7001 [2024-05-16T14:23:34Z INFO edgeless_apt1:grpc_lmpl1:controller] Start ControllerAPI GRPC Server at http://192.168.11.2:7001 </pre>	<pre> -Edgeless_node (TRUSTED) [SCONE] Using the following values (default values or specified in the untrusted environment): SCONE_QUEUEs=4 SCONE_SLOTS=256 SCONE_SIGPIPE=0 SCONE_WPAID2BIT=0 SCONE_ESPMS=100 SCONE_SSLEEP=4000 SCONE_CONFIGs/etc/sgx-nu1.conf SCONE_TCcs=8 SCONE_LOG-MARKING SCONE_HEAP=67108864 SCONE_STACK=2097152 SCONE_ESPMS=10000 SCONE_NODEs=hw SCONE_ALLOW_DLOPEN=no SCONE_HPROTECT=no SCONE_FORK=no SCONE_FORK_OS=0 SCONE_CONFIG_ID: <not specified> nu1 version: 1.2.4 [SCONE] version: 5.8.0 (2023-06-08 15:13:27) Enclave hash: 950443c05d82fe6b4cc3b19084d29c781d523b1021def10262f5edce9cdd44 [SCONE] src/enclave/dispatch.c:136:print_runtime_info(): Application runs in SGX debug mode. Its n entry can be read from outside the enclave with a debugger! THIS is not secure! [SCONE] src/syscall/syscall.c:31: _scone_n_syscall(): system call: memberbarrier, number 324 is not supported [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_node] Starting Edgeless Node [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_node:base_runtime:runtime] Starting Edgeless Runner [SCONE] src/shlding/fs_proc.c:478:proc_fs_open(): open: /proc/upline is not supported [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_apt1:grpc_lmpl1:invocation] Start InvocationAPI GRPC Server at htt p://192.168.11.2:7002 [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO warp::server] Server::run; addr=192.168.11.3:7003 [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO warp::server] listening on http://192.168.11.3:7003 [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_node:agent] Starting Edgeless Agent [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_apt1:grpc_lmpl1:agent] Start AgentAPI GRPC Server at http://192.16 8.11.3:7001 [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_node] Registering this node 'fda6ce79-46df-4f96-8bd2-456f720f606c' on e-ORC http://192.168.11.2:7011, capabilities: 12 Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-10710U CPU @ 1.10GHz CPU(s) a t 3899 BogoMIPS, 1 core(s), 0 MB memory, labels [], TEE, runtimes [RUST_WASH] [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_node] this node 'fda6ce79-46df-4f96-8bd2-456f720f606c' registered to e-ORC 'http://192.168.11.2:7011' </pre>
<pre> -u-ORC /home/user/edgeless/target/debug # RUST_LOG=Info ./edgeless_orc_d [2024-05-16T14:23:34Z INFO edgeless_orc] Starting Edgeless Orchestrator at http://192.168.11.2:7011 [2024-05-16T14:23:34Z INFO edgeless_orc] node keep-alive enabled every 2 seconds [2024-05-16T14:23:34Z INFO edgeless_orc::orchestration_logic] Orchestration logic strategy: random [2024-05-16T14:23:34Z INFO edgeless_apt1:grpc_lmpl1:orc] Start OrchestratorAPI GRPC Server at ht tp://192.168.11.2:7011 [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_orc::orchestrator] new resource advertised by node fda6ce79-46df-4 f96-8bd2-456f720f606c: provider_id http-ingress-1, class_type http-ingress, outputs [new_request] [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_orc::orchestrator] new resource advertised by node fda6ce79-46df-4 f96-8bd2-456f720f606c: provider_id http-egress-1, class_type http-egress, outputs [] [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_orc::orchestrator] new resource advertised by node fda6ce79-46df-4 f96-8bd2-456f720f606c: provider_id file-log-1, class_type file-log, outputs [] [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_orc::orchestrator] new resource advertised by node fda6ce79-46df-4 f96-8bd2-456f720f606c: provider_id redis-1, class_type redis, outputs [] [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_orc::orchestrator] added function instance client: node_id fda6ce7 9-46df-4f96-8bd2-456f720f606c, agent URL http://192.168.11.3:7021, invocation URL http://192.168.11.3:7 002, capabilities 12 Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-10710U CPU @ 1.10GHz CPU(s) at 3899 BogoMIPS, 1 core(s), 0 MB memory, labels [], TEE, runtimes [RUST_WASH] </pre>	<pre> [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_node] Creating resource 'http-egress-1' [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_node] Creating resource 'file-log-1' [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_node] Creating resource 'redis-1' [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_node:agent] new runner, class_type: RUST_WASH [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_node:base_runtime:runtime] Starting Edgeless Runner [SCONE] src/shlding/fs_proc.c:478:proc_fs_open(): open: /proc/upline is not supported [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_apt1:grpc_lmpl1:invocation] Start InvocationAPI GRPC Server at htt p://192.168.11.2:7002 [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO warp::server] Server::run; addr=192.168.11.3:7003 [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO warp::server] listening on http://192.168.11.3:7003 [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_node:agent] Starting Edgeless Agent [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_apt1:grpc_lmpl1:agent] Start AgentAPI GRPC Server at http://192.16 8.11.3:7001 [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_node] Registering this node 'fda6ce79-46df-4f96-8bd2-456f720f606c' on e-ORC http://192.168.11.2:7011, capabilities: 12 Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-10710U CPU @ 1.10GHz CPU(s) a t 3899 BogoMIPS, 1 core(s), 0 MB memory, labels [], TEE, runtimes [RUST_WASH] [2024-05-16T14:23:36Z INFO edgeless_node] this node 'fda6ce79-46df-4f96-8bd2-456f720f606c' registered to e-ORC 'http://192.168.11.2:7011' </pre>
<pre> -CLI /home/user/edgeless/target/debug # /home/user/edgeless/target/debug # </pre>	

Fig. 3. EDGELESS_NODE trusted image establishes a connection with the rest of the EDGELESS System

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